

MIXED MODE DELAMINATION IN UNIDIRECTIONAL GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITE UNDER STATIC AND FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The mixed mode I+II delamination in unidirectional Glass/Epoxy under static and fatigue loading was investigated by using MMB specimens. The loading of MMB specimen was simply a combination of DCB pure mode I and ENF pure mode II, so the analyses developed for these pure modes could be directly used to reduce MMB test data. The total critical strain energy release rate calculated from a linear or nonlinear models were compared with experimental measurement using the compliance calibration method so as to ensure the analytical models for validity. Due to this last method, the increase of fracture resistance as crack growth was observed for several mixed mode as well. The mixed mode fracture toughness G_{TC} obtained from MMB tests showed an excellent agreement by comparison of the results obtained from IDCB tests. So the G_{TC} to be independent of test configuration seemed to be confirmed. An empirical criterion and a semi-empirical criterion could be applied to predict the mixed mode delamination behaviour. The MMB tests were also performed under fatigue loading at $R=0.1$, $\omega=3\text{Hz}$ for mixed mode $G_{II}/G_T=90\%$. The delamination growth rate (da/dN) was described by using Paris's law.

Keywords: DELAMINATION, MIXED MODE, FRACTURE ENERGY, GLASS/EPOXY

1. INTRODUCTION

The most critical failure in composite structures is delamination between plies. This failure has been often characterized by a material's delamination fracture toughness, expressed in term of the critical strain energy release rate G_c . In the most cases, delamination in structures is a result of mixed mode I+II loading and its toughness has been found strongly dependant of the mixed mode ratio G_I/G_{II} (or G_{II}/G_{I+II}). It is therefore important to characterize the delamination fracture in a large range of the mixed mode ratio. For this purpose, several mixed mode I+II delamination tests have been proposed in the literature [1-11], among these tests the Mixed-Mode Bending (MMB) test proposed by Reeder and Crews [9-11] seems of great advantages: first, a wide range of mixed mode ratio can be produced with the same geometry of specimens; secondly, a simple model based on the beam theory can offer satisfactory results for mode I and mode II components: G_I , G_{II} ; thirdly, the mixed mode ratio was found independent of the crack length and the applied load, the former allows us to study the crack growth resistance and the latter to study the fatigue behaviour for one desired mixed mode.

In this work, by using the MMB specimens, the mixed mode I+II delamination fracture toughness of a unidirectional Glass/Epoxy was measured under static loading in a wide range of mixed mode ratio. And then this test was exploited for investigating the fatigue mixed mode delamination.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material used in this study was a Glass E/Epoxy M10 composite (VICOTEX M10/38%/1130). Their elastic constants were:

$$\begin{array}{lll} E_{11}=36.2 \text{ GPa} & G_{12}= 5.6 \text{ GPa} & \nu_{12}=0.26 \\ E_{22}=10.6 \text{ GPa} & G_{13}= 3.7 \text{ GPa} & \nu_{13}=0.33 \\ E_{33}= 7.2 \text{ GPa} & G_{23}= 3.2 \text{ GPa} & \nu_{23}=0.48 \end{array}$$

Each of them was measured experimentally [12]. The test specimens of the width $B= 20\text{mm}$ and the length $L=150\text{mm}$ were produced from a quasi-unidirectional 16-ply panel (5% fibres woven). The normal thickness was 6mm. The delamination starter of the specimen was a Teflon film placed

between the 8th and 9th plies. Hinges were bonded to the end of the specimens and the load was applied to the specimen by means of a lever where the distance, c , between the load-point and the lever fulcrum can be varied. Figure 1 shows schematically the MMB test apparatus. This apparatus was designed under consideration of minimizing the nonlinearity [10, 11].

Figure 1. Mixed mode bending test apparatus

2.1 Static MMB Tests

The static MMB tests were performed at room temperature. The specimens were loaded in displacement control at a rate of 2mm/min at the lever loading point. The onset of delamination growth was detected simultaneously by acoustic emissions and a strain gage placed just over the crack tip. Critical point at the onset of delamination growth corresponds closely the first acoustic emissions, where the strain gage response as well as the load-displacement response changed suddenly their slope. These techniques could identify well the onset of delamination [6-8], and the correspondent load P_{cr} was used in the calculation of G_I , G_{II} and G_{TC} (total critical value).

2.1.1. Analysis

In fact the MMB test simply combines the mode I DCB (Double Cantilever Beam) and mode II ENF (Edge Notch Flexure) tests. Mode I, Mode II contributions: G_I , G_{II} as well as the mixed mode ratio G_{II}/G_T depend on the distance c (Fig.1). A linear analysis based on the beam theory has been developed by Reeder and Crews [9], the contribution of mode I and mode II to the critical total strain energy release rate can be calculated by introducing the critical load P_{cr} in the following relations:

$$(G_I)_{Lin} = \frac{4P^2(3c-L)^2}{64BL^2E_{11}I} \left[a^2 + \frac{2a}{\lambda} + \frac{1}{\lambda^2} + \frac{h^2E_{11}}{10G_{13}} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$(G_{II})_{Lin} = \frac{3P^2(c+L)^2}{64BL^2E_{11}I} \left[a^2 + \frac{h^2E_{11}}{5G_{13}} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$(G_T)_{Lin} = (G_I)_{Lin} + (G_{II})_{Lin} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{where } \lambda = \frac{1}{h} \left(\frac{6E_{33}}{E_{11}} \right)^{1/4}$$

In order to account for the geometry nonlinearity of the MMB loading apparatus, a nonlinear analysis was developed in Ref 10 and 11. The G equations were given to account for rotations about the crack tip and the shear deformation.

$$(G_I)_{NL} = \frac{M_I^2}{BE_{II}I} \left[1 + \frac{2}{\lambda a} + \frac{1}{(\lambda a)^2} \right] + \frac{6P_I^2}{5B^2G_{13}h} \quad (4)$$

$$(G_{II})_{NL} = \frac{3M_{II}^2}{4BL^2E_{II}I} + \frac{9P_{II}^2}{80B^2G_{13}h} \quad (5)$$

$$(G_T)_{NL} = (G_I)_{NL} + (G_{II})_{NL} \quad (6)$$

Where M_I and M_{II} are the moments symmetrically and antisymmetrically applied to the two arms with regard to the crack and P_I and P_{II} represent the loading that would be applied to the specimen to obtain a pure mode I (DCB) or a pure mode II (ENF) test. The determination of these terms is described in Ref.10.

In our work, both the linear nonlinear models were used for the calculation of G_I , G_{II} and G_{TC} in confirmation of the small effect of geometry nonlinearity of our test apparatus.

2.1.2. Compliance Calibration

The previous studies on MMB tests [9-11] have indicated that the mixed mode ratio is virtually invariable with the crack length and it depends only on the distance, c , between the load-point and the lever fulcrum (Fig.1). So for a given mixed mode (c constant) the compliances of the load point, $C = \delta/P$, for different initial crack length, a , were measured from the load-displacement response to calibrate experimentally the compliance law, $C=F(a)$. Based on the linear analysis, the experimental compliance laws of the MMB specimens used in this work were expressed as:

$$C_{exp} = \alpha + \beta a^3 \quad (7)$$

Where the material constants α and β were mixed mode ratio dependent, they were determined by interpolating the measured compliances. The figure 2 presents the results of experimental compliance calibration for several mixed modes.

Fig.2 Compliances (C) versus the crack length (a) to the power 3

And then the G_{TC} can be calculated by the compliance method:

$$G_{TC} = \frac{P_c^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da} = \frac{3\beta a^2 P_c^2}{2B} \quad (8)$$

The G_{TC} values so determined were a results of the measurements of a , initial crack length, P_c , critical load at the onset of delamination and C , compliance of the system. They could be used to verify experimentally the analytical models for G_{TC} . Moreover, an another advantage of this method is that the delamination resistance G_R as the crack growth can be characterized. Once the constants α and β were obtained for a given mixed mode (c =constant), effective crack length, a_{eff} , during the crack growth, can be calculated as follows:

$$a_{\text{eff}} = \left(\frac{C_R - \alpha}{\beta} \right)^{1/3} \quad (9)$$

where C_R is the compliance after the onset of delamination. It can be measured on the corresponding load, P_R , and displacement, δ_R , during the crack propagation, we have then: $C_R = \delta_R / P_R$. The crack propagation resistance G_P can be obtained using:

$$G_R = \frac{P_R^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da} = \frac{3\beta a_{\text{eff}}^2 P_R^2}{2B} \quad (10)$$

2.2 Fatigue MMB Tests

The mixed mode delamination behaviour of composite materials under fatigue loading will be probably influenced by several loading parameters, such as cyclic load ratio R , frequency ω and the mixed mode ratio. To understand their effects, it is interesting to realize a fatigue delamination test under a constant mixed mode ratio. Recall that the mixed mode ratio in the MMB delamination tests is independent on the applied load, this type of specimens is therefore very appropriate to fatigue delamination tests, because it will suffice to choose a corresponding distance c for one mixed mode ratio desired and this ratio don't varies throughout the testing.

As beginning, the constant-amplitude of the applied load MMB fatigue tests was conducted on the unidirectional Glass/Epoxy composite with the mixed mode ratio G_{II}/G_T equal to 90% at $R=0.1$ and $\omega=3$ Hz. The tests were load-controlled and the maximum cyclic loads P_{max} were selected to be approximately 30%, 48% and 67% of the static critical load P_{cr} , these loads induced stable crack propagation.

The dimensions of specimens were the same as those for static tests, the initial crack lengths were 25mm. The delamination threshold was detected visually as well as by means of an acoustic emission receptor and the corresponding number of cycles N_{cr} was recorded. During the crack growth, the delamination lengths, a , which were determined by observing the edge of the specimens with the help of a binocular, were recorded as a function of the number of cycles N and were used to calculate the ΔG_T :

$$\Delta G_T = \frac{(P_{\text{max}} - P_{\text{min}})^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da} = \frac{3\beta a^2 (P_{\text{max}} - P_{\text{min}})^2}{2B} \quad (11)$$

3. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

3.1 Total Critical Strain Energy Release Rate, G_{TC} , Under Static MMB Loading

Once the critical loads P_{cr} at the onset of delamination were measured during tests, the mixed mode fracture toughness of Glass/Epoxy could be determined in the three ways:

- linear analysis $G_{\text{TC-Lin}}$ (Eqs. 1-3);
- nonlinear analysis $G_{\text{TC-NL}}$ (Eqs. 4-6);
- and experimental compliance calibration $G_{\text{TC-Exp}}$ (Eq.8).

As for the mixed mode ratio, only the two analytical models could give the results. Here we note $(G_{II}/G_{\text{TC}})_{\text{Lin}}$ and $(G_{II}/G_{\text{TC}})_{\text{NL}}$ for the linear and nonlinear calculations, respectively.

The table 1 gives these results, where

$$E1(G_{\text{TC}}) = \frac{G_{\text{TC-Exp}} - G_{\text{TC-Lin}}}{G_{\text{TC-Exp}}} \% \quad (12)$$

$$E2(G_{\text{TC}}) = \frac{G_{\text{TC-Exp}} - G_{\text{TC-NL}}}{G_{\text{TC-Exp}}} \% \quad (13)$$

$$E3\left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{\text{TC}}}\right) = \frac{\left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{\text{TC}}}\right)_{\text{NL}} - \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{\text{TC}}}\right)_{\text{Lin}}}{\left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{\text{TC}}}\right)_{\text{NL}}} \% \quad (14)$$

Table 1 Results of the mixed mode fracture toughness of Glass/Epoxy

c (mm)	a (mm)	P _{cr} (N)	G _{TC} -Lin (J/m ²)	G _{TC} -NL (J/m ²)	G _{TC} -Exp (J/m ²)	($\frac{G_{II}}{G_{TC}}$)-Lin %	($\frac{G_{II}}{G_{TC}}$)-NL %	E1(G _{TC}) %	E2(G _{TC}) %	E3($\frac{G_{II}}{G_{TC}}$) %
30	30	568.0	993.9	1045.1	1963.9	89.97	92.41	49.39	46.78	2.65
30	45	382.0	1004.2	1046.5	1998.6	90.51	90.94	49.75	47.64	0.47
40	36	400.0	1113.6	1161.5	1232.2	70.01	71.86	9.63	5.74	2.58
40	37	368.0	994.3	1034.5	1101.7	70.10	71.84	9.75	6.10	2.43
40	40	400.0	1368.0	1423.5	1521.3	70.33	70.37	10.07	6.43	0.05
50	35	244.0	610.8	666.5	648.9	53.86	52.82	5.88	-2.70	-1.96
50	35	242.0	600.8	654.5	638.4	53.86	52.88	5.88	-2.53	-1.84
60	42	174.0	652.1	657.0	654.9	43.62	42.80	0.42	-0.30	-1.92
60	45	144.0	510.1	525.2	514.9	43.84	42.42	0.94	-2.00	-3.35
90	25	118.0	280.1	253.4	240.7	25.49	28.11	-16.38	-5.26	9.33
90	30	100.0	281.6	271.5	248.9	26.20	28.43	-13.14	-9.06	7.86

From this table, it can be seen that for both total critical strain energy release rate, G_{TC}, and mixed mode ratio, G_{II}/G_{TC}, the results obtained from linear analysis agree closely with those from the nonlinear calculation. The relative error in G_{TC} and G_{II}/G_{TC} determination is within 12% and 10%, respectively. The small geometrical nonlinearity of the apparatus used is therefore confirmed for the composite tested, so that a complex nonlinear analysis is no longer needed to reduce MMB data.

Compared to the experimental measurement of G_{TC} using compliance calibration method, in the majority of cases, linear and nonlinear models appear to provide acceptably accurate values. Excepting the case of 91% of mode II contribution, the relative error of G_{TC} between the experimental and linear analysis (Eq. 12) is less than 17%, and that between the experimental and nonlinear calculation is just less than 10%. However, in the case of important mode II contribution, the G_{TC} results are rather unexpected seeing that the experimental value G_{TC-Exp} is perhaps double of an analytical one. For verification, the G_{TC-Exp} measured in MMB tests were plotted versus the mixed mode ratio G_{II}/G_{TC} in the figure 3 where we reported the G_{TC} values measured on the same composite by using an another type of mixed mode specimen named IDCB as well. The IDCB tests have been developed in the previous studies [12,13]. The pure mode I (DCB) and pure mode II (ENF and CLS) results were also presented in this figure so as to study the mixed mode fracture resistance in the range of G_{II}/G_{TC} varying from 0 to 100%.

Fig. 3 Mixed mode fracture toughness as a function of percent mixed mode ratio

By comparison, all of the G_{TC} measurement from MMB tests have a good agreement with the IDCB test results, G_{TC-Exp} values in mixed mode G_{II}/G_{TC}=91% is therefore believed to be correctly measured. But why in this case analytical models gives the G_{TC} value so much lower? what is the error source and how will be eliminated this error? For giving a reasonable response to these questions, a lot of studies in both experimental and analytical aspects will be required.

The excellent agreement of the MMB test results compared with those from the IDCB tests indicates an independence of testing type for the G_{TC} measurement. In other words, the total critical strain energy release rate dose represent the intrinsic resistance of material to the onset of delamination. This resistance increases slightly with the mixed mode ratio until mode II contribution is in neighbourhood of 45%. After this range, G_{TC} increases significantly against the mixed mode ratio G_{II}/G_{TC} , where the mode II contribution seems play an important role in the fracture resistance.

In order to predict the mixed mode delamination toughness as a function of G_{II}/G_{TC} , an empirical criterion was suggested [12] in form of:

$$G_{TC} = G_{IC} + (G_{IIC} - G_{IC}) \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{TC}} \right)^m \quad (15)$$

where $G_{TC}(P_{cr}) = G_I(P_{cr}) + G_{II}(P_{cr})$. By interpolating the measured points, this criterion with $m=2$ (dashed line) and $m=2.5$ (bold line) were reported in Fig.3, the latter could provide a criterion conservative.

Fig.4 Total critical strain energy release rate as a function of normalized mode II component

Based on the G_{TC} measurement, the study in Ref.12 has proposed a semi-empirical criterion which emphasizes the role of the mode II component in the mixed mode delamination. It is expressed by:

$$G_{TC} = G_{IC} + (G_{IIC} - G_{IC}) \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}} \right)^m \quad (16)$$

In Fig.4 we plot the G_{TC} values versus the normalized mode II component. It shows that all of points are localized between the criterion with $m=1$ and $m=2/3$. In fact, when $m=1$, the equation 16 becomes a criterion used largely in the literature: $\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}} = 1$.

3.2 Fracture Resistance G_R As Crack Propagation Under Static MMB Loading

Figure 5-A gives examples of R-curves, the change in fracture resistance G_R as the delamination was extended, for certain mixed mode ratios: $G_{II}/G_{TC} = 28\%$, 43% and 72% , obtained from MMB tests. They were determined using the Eqs. 9, 10. Clearly the greatest increase in G_R was found for $G_{II}/G_{TC} = 70\%$, while there was no significant difference between the cases of $G_{II}/G_{TC} = 28\%$ and 43% . No matter which mixed mode delamination, G_R was found to increase to a plateau, at which the fracture resistance nearly stabilized. The value corresponding to this plateau, G_S , seems dependent on the mixed mode ratio. In the range of small mode II contribution ($G_{II}/G_{TC} < 45\%$) where fracture toughness increased slightly (Fig.3), The G_S was nearly constant. When the mode II contribution became important, a significant increase in G_S value was observed. The increase of fracture resistance as crack propagates would be a result of the damage development around the crack tip and the effect of fibre bridging [3]. The stabilized fracture resistance G_S would be due to a certain saturation of these phenomena. Evidently, because of the complexities of mixed mode delamination process, the results obtained in our work were far from giving an quantitative explanation for the delamination extension.

In Fig.5-B, the G_R values versus the effective crack length from MMB tests were compared with those from MMF tests performed on the same composite in a previous study. Two types of specimens could give the same mixed mode ratio: $G_{II}/G_{TC}=43\%$. It is showed that two curves had almost the same slope as G_R increased, and the same G_S value. These mean that the R-curve would be material characteristic which is independent on the specimen configurations.

Fig.5-A G_R versus effective crack length from MMB tests

Fig.5-B G_R versus effective crack length from MMB and MMF tests

3.3 Fatigue MMB Test Results

During the fatigue MMB test, the measurement of the critical number of cycles, N_{Cr} , corresponding to the delamination threshold showed a considerably scatter. For example, N_{Cr} measured on several specimens having the same dimension, in the same loading condition ($P_{max}/P_{Cr}=50\%$), could vary from 680 to 15000. This variation is so important that it could be hardly explicated by the detecting technics. It seems that delamination threshold of the composite used was very sensible to the initial state of material.

Fig.6 Delamination growth rate (da/dN) as a function of ΔG_T for $G_{II}/G_T=90\%$

Fig.7 Delamination growth rate (da/dN) as a function of the crack length (a)

Plots of delamination growth rate (da/dN) as a function of ΔG_T in the case of mixed mode ratio $G_{II}/G_T=90\%$ are present in Fig.6. Power-law fits of the data (Paris's law) yielded the following relationship:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = 2.76 \cdot 10^{-12} (\Delta G_T)^{1.224} \quad (\text{mm/N}) \quad (17)$$

where ΔG_T was determined by substituting $(P_{max} - P_{min})$ into Eq.8, it was expressed in J/m^2 . However, if the delamination growth rate (da/dN) are plotted versus the crack length (a) (Fig.7), the first fatigue data in mixed mode $G_{II}/G_T=40\%$ decreases as the crack grows, which is contrary to that

in mixed mode $G_{II}/G_T=90\%$. Evidently, the fatigue tests on MMB specimens described here is only a beginning, the verification of the equation 17 and l'explination of the different variation of the (da/dN) in mixed mode case requires still more experimental data. The fatigue tests are carrying out in a wide range of mixed mode ratio so as to predict the mixed mode fatigue delamination behaviour. The researches concerning the improvement of the test apparatus and the fracture detecting technics as well as the data reduction method are actually under way.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1- The MMB test is very promising for characterizing the mixed mode delamination both under static and fatigue loading because it can produce any desired mixed mode which is nearly invariable in face of crack length or applied load changes.

2- In the determination of G_{TC} , the linear and nonlinear models were confirmed, in the majority of cases, by the experimental compliance calibration method. The latter could be used to characterising the fracture resistance as the crack propagation.

3- The mixed mode delamination toughness of Glass/Epoxy could be predicted by an empirical criterion expressed by: $G_{TC} = G_{IC} + (G_{IIC}-G_{IC}) \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{TC}}\right)^2$ or un semi-empirical one expressed by:

$G_{TC} = G_{IC} + (G_{IIC}-G_{IC}) \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}}\right)^m$ with $2/3 < m < 1$. The fracture resistance G_R increased as the crack growth until a stable value G_S which seemed dependent of the mixed mode ratio.

4- Delamination growth rate (da/dN) in the case of mixed mode ratio $G_{II}/G_T=90\%$ could be described by the relationship: $\frac{da}{dN} = 2.76 \cdot 10^{-12} (\Delta G_T)^{1.224}$ (mm/N), where the unity of ΔG_T was $\frac{N}{m}$.

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